

Right to information in the energy crisis

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Electricity rationing disrupts the work of Ecuadorians, changes working hours, reduces production and generates uncertainty due to poor communication of the crisis.

The power cuts began with little or no warning. It was difficult to understand that the logic of supply and demand of electricity changes the schedules and duration of blackouts. Instead of notices, notes or fluent interviews, bulletins were presented about apparent sabotage and locating culprits.

At the same time, journalists and experts suggested plans and strategies for ministers and more public managers to communicate what happened and, as far as possible, households, and businesses to plan, but it took a long time for an explanation to reach citizens.

Questions and commitments remain to face new difficulties in which it is essential to know the structures of social communication through digital platforms, today affected by misinformation and minimal regulations.

On the basis of guarantees for freedom of expression, compromises must be sought to foster a public opinion that consolidates democracy. The right to public information is enshrined in Ecuadorian law, but in this instance, it was not respected. The government did not provide data, sources, and testimonies in time. How can governance be improved if the authorities do not respect the law? Citizens are aware that without quality information, their chances of getting better services at fair prices are diminished.

Perhaps the positive aspect of the electricity shortages is that the community is sensitive to identifying commitments and the fulfilment of political promises and, despite the imperfections, participation is measured by social networks.